

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Oxidation of Secondary Alcohols by Pyridinium Hydrobromide Perbromide

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The oxidation of secondary alcohols by pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide (PHPB) in aqueous acetic acid leads to the formation of the corresponding ketones. The reaction is first order with respect to PHPB and the alcohols. The reaction rates have been determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters calculated. The oxidation of benzhydrol- α -d exhibited a substantial kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 4.83$). With an increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solvent mixture of acetic acid and water, the rate increases. Addition of pyridinium hydrobromide and acrylonitrile has no effect on the rate. Suitable mechanisms have been proposed.

Pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide (PHPB) has been extensively used in synthetic organic chemistry as a brominating reagent and as a dehydrogenating reagent^{1,2}. There are not many reports on the mechanistic aspects of reactions of PHPB³⁻⁶. We have been interested in the study of kinetics and mechanism of oxidations by oxidants containing halogens. We report here the kinetics of oxidation of eight aliphatic secondary alcohols, 1-phenylethanol and benzhydrol by PHPB in aqueous acetic acid. Attempts have been made to correlate rate and structure in this reaction. Mechanistic aspects are discussed.

Results and Discussion

The rate and other experimental data were obtained for all the alcohols investigated. Since the results are similar, only representative data are reproduced here.

The reactions are of first order with respect to PHPB. Further, the values of k_{obs} are independent of the initial concentration of PHPB. The reaction rate increases linearly with an increase in the concentration of the alcohol (Table 1). To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of benzhydrol- α -d (PhCDOHPh) was studied. The oxidation of deuterated benzhydrol exhibits a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (Table 2). The

rates of oxidation of the alcohols were determined in solvents containing different proportions of acetic acid in the solvent mixture of acetic acid and water. It was found that the rate decreases with an increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solvent mixture (Table 3). Addition of pyridinium hydrobromide does not affect the rate (Table 4). This rules out the possibility of a pre-equilibrium involving pyridinium ion.

The oxidation of 2-propanol, under nitrogen atmosphere, failed to induce the polymerisation of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the reaction rate (Table 1).

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE OXIDATION OF PROPAN-2-OL BY PHPB AT 303 K

[2-PrOH] mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ [PHPB] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ k_{obs} s ⁻¹
0.03	3.0	1.82
0.06	3.0	3.70
0.12	3.0	7.20
0.24	3.0	14.6
0.36	3.0	21.6
0.48	3.0	29.4
0.36	3.0	22.0 ^a
0.24	1.5	13.8
0.24	4.5	14.9
0.24	6.5	14.3
0.24	8.5	15.0
0.24	9.8	14.8

^aContained 0.5 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile

TABLE 2—KINETIC ISOTOPE EFFECT IN THE OXIDATION OF BENZHYDROL BY PHPB AT 293 K

[PHPB] = 0.003 mol dm⁻³; [alcohol] = 0.06 mol dm⁻³

Compd.	10 ² k ₂ dm ⁶ mol ⁻² s ⁻¹	k _H /k _D
Benzhydrol	13.1	
Benzhydrol-α-d	2.71	4.83

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON THE OXIDATION OF 2-PROPANOL

[2-PrOH] = 0.24 mol dm⁻³, [PHPB] = 0.003 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 303 K

AcOH (% v/v)	25	40	50	60	72
10 ⁵ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	70.5	25.8	14.6	7.58	3.34

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF PYRIDINIUM HYDROBROMIDE ON THE OXIDATION OF 2-PROPANOL BY PHPB

[2-PrOH] = 0.24 mol dm⁻³, [PHPB] = 0.003 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 303 K

[PyHBr] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.05
10 ⁵ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	14.6	15.3	15.0	14.0	15.2

Thus a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely. The rates of oxidation of ten secondary alcohols were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters at 298 K were calculated (Table 5).

The activation enthalpies and entropies of the oxidation of the ten alcohols are linearly related ($r^2 = 0.9783$). The value of isokinetic temperature is 539 ± 28 K. The isokinetic relationship was tested and found genuine by applying Exner's criterion⁷. The Exner's plot between $\log k_2$ at 293 and 323 K is linear ($r^2 = 0.9984$, slope = 0.8073 ± 0.0115). The value of isokinetic temperature, calculated by Exner's method, is 567 ± 32 K, which is in excellent agreement with the value obtained

by the other method. A linear isokinetic correlation implies that all the alcohols are oxidised by the same mechanism.

In solution, PHPB may undergo the following reactions,

The probable oxidising species in a solution of PHPB are, therefore, PHPB itself, tribromide ion and molecular bromine. However, strict first order dependence on PHPB and the absence of any effect of pyridinium bromide on the rate of reaction ruled out both bromine and tribromide ion as the reactive oxidising species. Thus the most probable oxidising species is PHPB itself.

The increase in the rate of reaction with an increase in the polarity of the medium suggests that in the rate-determining step, the transition state is more polar than the reactant. A plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of relative permittivity, is non-linear. The solvent effect was analysed using Grunwald-Winstein⁸ equation (3),

$$\log k_2 = \log k_0 + mY \quad (3)$$

The plot of $\log k_2$ against Y is linear ($r^2 = 0.9970$) with $m = 0.71 \pm 0.02$. The value of m points to a transition state which is more polar than the reactant. Thus considerable charge separation takes place in the transition state of the rate-determining step.

TABLE 5—RATE CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF OXIDATION OF RCHOHMe BY PHPB

Subst.	10 ⁵ k ₂ (dm ⁶ mol ⁻² s ⁻¹)				ΔH^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^* J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^* kJ mol ⁻¹
	293 K	303 K	313 K	323 K			
Me	282	605	1 300	2 780	57.5 ± 0.8	-98 ± 3	86.6 ± 0.6
Et	550	1 100	2 240	4 390	56.8 ± 1.2	-95 ± 5	85.1 ± 1.9
Pr	1 100	2 160	4 230	8 320	50.5 ± 0.7	-111 ± 2	83.3 ± 0.6
i-Pr	2 230	4 000	7 180	12 300	42.4 ± 0.3	-132 ± 1	81.7 ± 0.3
iso-Bu	6 000	11 000	21 000	36 100	44.9 ± 0.6	-116 ± 2	79.2 ± 0.4
Bu	1 340	2 690	5 400	10 500	51.3 ± 0.5	-106 ± 2	82.8 ± 0.4
ClCH ₂	4.12	11.0	33	94.6	79.5 ± 1.2	-58 ± 3	96.7 ± 1.0
MeOCH ₂	43.3	102	245	565	64.9 ± 0.8	-88 ± 2	91.1 ± 0.6
Ph	10 400	17 800	30 600	51 700	39.6 ± 0.5	-129 ± 2	78.0 ± 0.4
Benzhydrol	13 100	21 300	35 500	58 100	36.6 ± 0.6	-137 ± 2	77.4 ± 0.5

Correlation analysis of reactivity : The rates of oxidation of the aliphatic alcohols failed to yield significant correlations separately with Taft's⁹ σ^* and E_s values [eqns. (4) and (5)],

$$\log k = -2.74 (\pm 0.36) \sigma^* - 1.95 \quad (4)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9060; \text{sd} = 0.42; n = 8; \psi = 0.23$$

$$\log k = -2.35 (\pm 1.40) E_s - 3.06 \quad (5)$$

$$r^2 = 0.3180; \text{sd} = 1.13; n = 8; \psi = 0.71$$

here n is the number of data points and ψ the Exner's statistical parameter¹⁰. The rates were, therefore, correlated in terms of the Pavelich-Taft¹¹ dual substituent-parameter equation (6),

$$\log k_2 = \rho^* \sigma^* + \delta E_s + \log k_0 \quad (6)$$

The values of the substituent constants were obtained from the compilation by Wiberg¹². The correlations are excellent, reaction constants being negative (Table 6). There is no significant collinearity ($r^2 = 0.2136$) between σ^* and E_s of the eight substituents. The negative polar reaction constant indicates an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state of the rate-determining step. The negative steric reaction constant shows a steric acceleration of the reaction. This may be explained on the basis of the high ground-state energy of the sterically crowded alcohols. Since the crowding is relieved in the product ketone as well as in the transition state leading to it, the transition state energies of the crowded and uncrowded alcohols do not differ much and steric acceleration, therefore, results. The faster oxidations of 1-phenylethanol and benzhydrol may well be due to the stabilisation of the electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state by phenyl groups through resonance.

TABLE 6—TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF THE REACTION CONSTANTS

T K	ρ^*	δ	r^2	sd	ψ
293	-1.99 ± 0.02	-1.09 ± 0.02	0.999 8	0.02	0.012
303	-1.86 ± 0.02	-1.02 ± 0.01	0.999 7	0.02	0.014
313	-1.73 ± 0.03	-1.00 ± 0.04	0.999 3	0.03	0.022
323	-1.59 ± 0.04	-0.94 ± 0.05	0.998 4	0.04	0.033

Mechanism : There is no kinetic evidence for the formation of an intermediate complex in the present reaction, however, its formation in small amounts can not be ruled out. In the oxidation

of primary aliphatic alcohols and aldehydes by PHPB^{5,6}, we observed Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to the reductant and suggested the formation of an intermediate complex in a pre-equilibrium. It is proposed that in the present reaction also an intermediate complex is formed in a rapid pre-equilibrium but the equilibrium constant is very small. The presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 4.83$ at 293 K) confirms that the α -C-H bond is cleaved in the rate-determining step. In view of the absence of any effect of radical scavenger, acrylonitrile, on the reaction rate, it is unlikely that a one-electron reaction giving rise to free radicals, is operative in this oxidation. Presently, it is not possible to state definitely about the nature of the intermediate complex. Heasley *et al.*¹³ proposed that in the reaction of PHPB with alkenes, a π -complex is formed by an interaction of the π bond of the alkene and PHPB. Formation of similar complexes has earlier been proposed by us also^{5,6}. The formation of a hypobromite ester (eqn. 7) is unlikely in view of the nil effect of pyridinium hydrobromide on the rate,

Thus on the basis of the above experimental data, a mechanism is proposed in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Alternatively, the reaction may involve an intermolecular hydride ion transfer in the rate-determining step (Scheme 2).

Experimental

All the alcohols (commercial, Fluka) were dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and then fractionated. Benzhydrol was recrystallised from ethanol. PHPB was prepared by the reported method¹⁴. Benzhydrol- α -d (PhCDOHPh) was also prepared by the reported method¹⁵. Its isotopic purity, as ascertained by its nmr spectra, was $94 \pm 5\%$. Acetic acid was refluxed with CrO_3 and acetic anhydride for 3 h and then distilled.

Product analysis : The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. In a typical experiment, 2-propanol (0.05 mol) and PHPB (0.01 mol) were made up to 100 ml in 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water and kept in the dark for *ca* 10 h to ensure completion of the reaction. The solution was then treated with an excess (200 ml) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (2 mol dm^{-3}) in HCl and kept overnight in a refrigerator. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, weighed, recrystallised from ethanol and weighed again. The yields of DNP before and after recrystallisation were 2.05 g (86%) and 1.77 g (74%) respectively. The DNP was found identical (m.p. and m.m.p.) with the DNP of acetone. Similar experiments were performed with other alcohols also. The overall reaction may be written as

Kinetic measurements : Reactions were carried out under pseudo-first - order conditions by maintaining a large excess of the alcohol ($\times 15$ or more) over PHPB. The solvent was 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water mixture, unless mentioned otherwise. The reactions were carried out at a constant temperature ($\pm 0.1 \text{ K}$) and were followed upto 80% reaction by monitoring the decrease in [PHPB] at 358 nm. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were

computed from linear ($r > 0.990$) least-squares plot of $\log [\text{PHPB}]$ vs time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The second order constant (k_2) was obtained by the relation, $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{alcohol}]$.

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